

STRENGTH EVALUATION OF T-JOINT STRUCTURES FOR THE COMPOSITE BOGIE FRAME UNDER BENDING

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1 Introduction

Adhesive composite joints nowadays play an important role in railroad components, aerospace and wind turbine. Accurate failure predictions are required for efficient joint design and to utilize the advantages of adhesive bonding, such as a more uniform stress distribution in the joint area, or less weight of the total structure when compare to mechanical fasteners. However, structural adhesives cannot be used directly as a substitute for mechanical fasteners. Due to a lack of understanding of damage initiation, propagation and different failure modes, the usage of composite materials remains below potential. Hence necessity of evaluating the damage progression of the composite material between first and final failure is clear. As analysis on composite joints has mostly concentrated on mechanical fasteners, the potential for validation and optimization regarding adhesive joints is relatively unexplored.

Adhesively bonded composite structures are especially prone to delamination failure as a result of a high gradient of peel stresses the end of overlap regions or through-thickness load transfer. The through-thickness strength of composites is usually low compared to the in-plane strength due to the absence of load-bearing fibers across the bonded surfaces.

In this study, the failure strength and modes of T-joints used in a composite bogie frame has been evaluated under a bending load. The bending load is corresponding to a traction load applied to the cross beams of the composite bogie frame. The composite bogie frame is composed of two side beams and two cross beams [6-7]. In order to make the composite bogie frame, first, the two cross beams and the two side beams were assembled by adhesively bonded method. Then, GEP224 glass/epoxy prepregs were

laid up on the surface of the assembled structure to form the skin. In this study, two types of T-joints were fabricated and tested. The first one is a T-joint in which a cross beam and a side beam are connected using only adhesive bonding method. The second one is a T-joint in which a cross beam and a side beam are assembled using adhesive bonding and skin layup.

Fig.1. T-joints of the composite bogie frame.

2 T-Joint Test

2.1 Preparations of Joint Specimens

For the fabrication of the adhesive only T-joint specimens, a steel mould with cross sectional dimensions of 140mmx140mm was manufactured. Then, the GEP224 glass/epoxy prepregs was laid up to the target thickness of 15mm. After the lay-up, it was sealed and pressured using a vacuum bag. Next, it was cured in an autoclave. After the curing of it, it was bonded with a side beam part made of the same prepreg using EPIKOTETM MGS[®] BPR 135G epoxy resin (Hexion, Germany). In case of the joints with

the adhesive bonding and skin layup, two same size tubes with the inner cross sectional dimensions of 140mmx140mm and thickness of 15mm were manufactured and they were bonded with each other using EPIKOTE™ MGS® BPR 135G epoxy resin. Then, the GEP224 glass/epoxy prepregs was laid up on the assembled part to the target thickness of 15mm. The average thickness of the adhesive layer in the two types of joint was 4mm.

2.2 Test Setup

In order to apply the bending load to the exact loading point of the T-joints, a steel beam was fastened with the T-joint using bolts as shown in Fig. 2. The T-joint was fixed on the fixing jig using the mechanical fastening. For the bending load application, a 5-ton capacity hydraulic actuator (MTS, USA) for the adhesive only joint and a 25-ton capacity hydraulic actuator (MTS, USA) for the joint with the adhesive bonding and skin layup were used. The deflection at the end of the T-joint was measured using a LVDT (Tokyo Sokki, Japan), which was located in the bottom of the joint. The loading rate of the test was 0.5mm/sec.

Fig.2. Test setup for the T-joint bending test.

Strain gauges were located critical points(Fig.3.) for getting a distributed stress in joint.

Fig.3. Location of Strain gauges : (a) adhesive only joint, (b) joint with the adhesive bonding and skin layup.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Test Result

Fig. 4 presents the load-displacement curves of the both joints. In case of the adhesive only joints (Fig. 4(a)), the average failure load was 3.75kN and average displacement was 0.885mm. The load-displacement curves of the adhesive only joint until first failure increased linearly.

Fig. 4. Load-displacement curves : (a) adhesive only joint, (b) joint with the adhesive bonding and skin layup.

Fig. 5 shows load-strain curve in critical points. Most of strain values in Fig.5(a) were increased linearly. Strain curve of Fig.5(b) shows small drop due to inside of the adhesive bond layer occurred crack.

Fig. 5. Load-strain curves : (a) adhesive only joint, (b) joint with the adhesive bonding and skin layup.

The initial crack of specimen 1 was observed at the corner region of the adhesive bond layer on the top section under tensile bending load and then they extended rapidly other regions (Fig. 6(a)). However, the initial crack of specimen 2 was observed overall top section of adhesive bond layer (Fig. 6(b)).

Through inspection of the fractured surface, interfacial failure was dominant in the specimen 1 (Fig. 7(a)), while delamination failure occurred on the top layer of the side beam part in the specimen 2 (Fig. 7(b)).

Fig.6. Joint crack propagation mode

Table.1 shows strain value averages of adhesive only joint about critical point. Strain values of Specimens were measured 3.31kN and 3.75kN respectively due to a few of strain value occurred error in specimen 1.

Fig. 7. Fractured surface of adhesive only joint : (a) specimen 1 (b) specimen 2.

In case of the joints with the adhesive bonding and skin layup (Fig. 4(b)), the average failure load was 67.94kN. The load-displacement curves of the joint showed a small load drop at 25.1kN and 29.0kN, respectively. The load-displacement curves behaved nonlinearly after the load drop. The initial cracks were observed at the corner regions on the top section under tensile bending load (Fig. 8(b)).

Fig. 8. Joint failure modes: (a) adhesive only joint, (b) joint with the adhesive bonding and skin layup.

The cracks grew along the top section and then started to propagate along the side of the T-joint accompanying with the fiber breakage.

3.2 Comparison of Test Result and FEM Model

In this study, the static structural analysis of the adhesive only joint was done using ABAQUS, a finite element analysis program. Fig. 8 shows the FEM model used for structural global behavior analysis of joint.

Fig. 9. The FEM model

Half modeling was used due to the joint was bilateral symmetry. In order to set up as same analysis conditions with test FEM model was used contact, bolt pre-tension condition. For comparison value of displacement in equivalent stress(3.75kN) which was average failure load was converted to distributed load as 156kN/m². From the static structural analysis results, the value of displacement was 0.920mm. The value was showed 3.9% displacement deviation with test value(Fig. 10).

Fig. 10. Displacement-force curve

	Test	FEM	Error(%)
C21-X	2870.3	3406.5	16.5
C22-X	2582.9	4928.4	47.6
C22-Y	-252.2	-294.0	14.3
S11	686.9	697.5	30.7
S12	244.6	302.5	19.7

Table.1. Strain value average of adhesive only joint

Through inspection of the fracture mode with strain value in adhesive only joint, specimen 1 was manufactured non-uniform distribution adhesive layer and specimen 2 was manufactured uniform distribution adhesive layer(Fig.6). Therefore, stress concentration of specimens occurred at the corner and center of the adhesive bond layer in the top section respectively. FEM model analysis result of strain values also occurred similar with test results(Table. 1).

Adhesive bond layer of specimens were made by hand grinding and FEM model was modeled accurately. Thus, a few of large errors occurred in strain values.

Fig. 11. Normal stress distribution

4 Conclusions

In this study, the failure loads for the adhesive only joints and the joint with the adhesive bonding and skin layup were measured through the bending test. From the test result, it was clear that the joint with the adhesive bonding and skin layup had a safety margin of 2.86 taking into account the traction load of 23.8kN.

In addition, the average failure load of two types of T-joints was 3.75kN and 67.94kN respectively. The crack behavior, the measured force-displacement curve, and the measured strains agree well with the FEM model analysis result.

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